

THE USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AS HEADLINES OF MASS MEDIA

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7769073>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17^t March 2023

Accepted: 24th March 2023

Online: 25th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Phraseological units (PhUs), phraseological variants, phraseological stability, stable word combine. It is known that a newspaper headline is a specific linguistic phenomenon

ABSTRACT

The article deals with analyzing types of phraseological units (PhUs) used in newspaper headlines, and their translation difficulties in the English newspaper headlines. The conclusions were confirmed by authentic examples from the sources above. The study of these peculiarities by students contributes to the process of both teaching and learning English as a communicative system, making it easier for both sides.

An article in a newspaper has an impact function as a journalistic text, which is an informative function combined with news and news. The publication of a newspaper implies a certain formation of the communicative core of a linguistic person, as well as the necessary qualities of good speech of the subjects of written communication. As the most common type of mass media, the main features of newspaper language are as follows:

- 1) economy of language tools with informative richness of the text;
- 2) Selection of language tools, focusing on specific communicative qualities of speech (accuracy, accuracy, consistency, relevance, richness and variety of language units, accessibility, impact, expressiveness, imagery);
- 3) Use of speech stereotypes characteristic of this style;
- 4) Due to the variety of topics and genres of the texts, the features of journalistic style are combined with other style features;
- 5) Use of various figurative and expressive means of the language;
- 6) Dialogicity, which includes taking into account the specific characteristics of the linguistic personality of the author and the potential reader.

A title as a text title or "title of work" is a micro text containing certain keywords. They carry the main semantic load and perform the text creation function. The lexical units of the title are the semantic centers of this text and are presented as keywords in the text itself. The title is extended to the text of a certain genre according to the standard model, that is, the intellectual product of the author is expressed in the linear opening of the text [25,257]. The title predetermines the choice of linguistic means: lexical units that act as keywords of the text are part of the associative field, while other words act as connecting elements and do not

create new meaning. The text-forming direction of the associative field: the associative field of the word is considered as the result of lexical connection. At the same time, the associative field does not differ from the text both in content and organization. In our work, we tried to analyze the reviews of similar headlines in different newspapers.

For example the first text: ***London students need memorial (Times, 07/11/2006).***

Students from the capital proposed to the city hall to install a statue of the open grade book as a symbol of good luck. At least part of the future monument should be cast from molten copper nickels, which are believed to bring good luck. The press service of the South-Eastern London Administrative District informed "Times" about the students' initiative.

The memorial can become a traditional meeting place for students and alumni. Its opening is proposed to coincide with Tatiana's Day, an unofficial student holiday celebrated on January 25. A monumental record book may appear in the capital in 2007. According to Regions.com, students want to see the monument in one of three places in the Southeast region: in Lefortovo near the Institute of Energy, in Vikhino near the University of Management, or in Kuzminki Park.

A famous student sign says: if on the eve of an exam you put an open notebook outside the window at midnight and shout "Freebie, come", the owner of the record book will get a good grade on the upcoming test. (4 words in the title and 138 words in the text: each word in the title has about 35 words).

Analyzing the second text: ***In Britain, a monument to the book of records appears (Sun 07/11/06).***

In London, a monument will be erected to the students' signs, said the representative of the capital's Southeast District Prefecture.

"The monument may appear next year. Students want its opening to coincide with Tatyana's Day. According to the students, such a monument will become a meeting place for both students and graduates of Moscow higher education institutions," said the representative of the prefecture. The source also noted that the open grade book will form the basis of the monumental composition. "As the initiators of this memorial say, one of the main superstitions of students is related to the record book. It is said that if you put your hand outside the window with an open notebook at midnight on the eve of the exam and shout "Freebie, come" in a loud voice, you are guaranteed a good grade, said the source.

The students suggested three places for the future monument: next to the London Energy Institute and the Technical University of Communication and Informatics in Lefortovo, next to the State University of Management in Vykchino, or in Kuzminki Park. (5/133 - 27 words).

Next text analysis: ***There will be a holiday on our street. London students need memorial (Independent, 11 July 2006).***

London students proposed to the city hall to install a statue of the open grade book as a symbol of good luck. Part of the future monument should be cast from molten copper nickels, which are believed to bring good luck. The press service of the South-Eastern administrative district informed the editors about the students' initiative. The monument can become a permanent meeting place for students and graduates of higher educational institutions of the capital. Its opening is scheduled for Tatiana's Day, which is an unofficial student holiday and is

celebrated on January 25. a clear student sign says: if on the eve of an exam you put an open notebook outside the window at midnight and shout "Freebie, come", the owner of the record book will get a good grade in the upcoming exam. (6 components/91 words - 15 words/component).

Since these texts are paradigmatically related, their sets of keywords match almost exactly. These high-frequency words are functionally important units, that is, they have the function of creating text. The potential for creating text is also found in the ratio of the number of words in the title and text: text 1 - 4/138 - 35 (about 35 words per title word), text 2 - 5/133 - 27 words, 3 text, - (6 components / 91 words - 15 words / component) word and title created on the basis of phraseological unit.

The most common typology of headings is a hierarchical classification focused on the linguistic means of their expression: word - phrase - sentence. "Grammar of the Russian language" notes that newspaper and other titles are very diverse in form: individual word forms or phrases, as well as a series of word forms, parts of a complex sentence, simple sentences can play this role" [30,421]. It is known that in modern mass media, headlines are mainly represented by a construction that corresponds in form to a simple sentence, which is related to its function of creating a text. At the same time, there is a need to develop a typology of headings based on a non-formal, functional feature - the laws of use of language units.

Functional-semantic types of information headers can be expressed as follows:

1. Indicative-informational title provides the minimum level of information presentation (minimum amount of information in the most general form, direction of the reader in the material).

Memorial to London students to appear (Daily Express, 07/11/2006). This header is information neutral. London students need a monument ("Observer", 07.11.2006). This title has a positive tone: students are active (should) in erecting a monument. It is in this text that the keyword initiative appears.

2. Self-informative refers to the necessary level of presentation of information to a potential reader within the scope of clarification and possibly partial interpretation of the information material. In this case, the common monument will receive a certain symbol in the book of records.

Evaluative and informative, the main semantic element is the evaluation of the fact (negative, neutral, positive). The level of negative and positive evaluation may differ. In the first version - positive: the signs are good, this is the unique world of youth - carelessness and carelessness, optimism; in the second version - the fact formed on the basis of the use of an uncoded lexical unit (freebie, sop) reflecting one of the general features of the English national character is enthusiastically evaluated.

As a means of creating a text, the title performs various communicative functions:

1) Attracts readers' attention, as well as directs potential readers in publication materials;

2) Serves as a guide, because it turns out to be very informative (in some cases, sufficiently informative: the reader only tries to clarify some facts;

3) Activates the recipient's basic knowledge;

4) He participates in creation by involving the student in the language game;

5) Provides preview (predicts perception and determines understanding of the text);

6) Forms and promotes an adequate attitude to the proposed material;

7) Promote equal communication between the subjects of communication due to the specific characteristics of the linguistic personality of the author and the potential reader (gender, age, social status, education, possible benefits of reading, etc.) provides

The evaluation, idiomaticity, and repetition of the phraseologism-title turn it into a broad and expressive element of journalistic material. It is often used as a phraseological title. However, the title consisting of a phraseological unit is under the pressure of phraseological meaning and does not have complete information: the indicative-informational title provides the minimum level of information presentation and determines the direction of the reader to the material. The context is used separately - as a graphic element, it does not give an idea of what will be discussed in the article. In this type of titles, the title included in the title set often contains the main semantic load.

Phraseological units - substantive, verbal and adverbial type headings are performed without headings. Perhaps the writer creates intrigue with an "ambiguous" title, directing the reader to the material - which forces the potential reader to refer to the text. Many turns of phrase are so transparent and frequent that they are easily picked up by potential readers. For example, the title and accompanying subtitle:

Yesterday, President Putin presented state awards to the best representatives of creative intellectuals. "Observer" (13.06.2007)

After leaving the presidency, Putin will remain at the top of the real power in Russia. "Financial Times" (26.08.2007)

Decisive action, calculated means to achieve success in something. "Financial Times" (26.08.2007)

A group of ex-combat swimmers crossed the Caspian.

Someone who is full of strength, energy to do something, can do something. Sun (1986: 345).

House prices in London will fall significantly, but only on insurance policies issued by the authorities. "Financial Times" (26.08.2007).

Phraseologism as a part of the title consists of sentences according to the structure of the content of modern newspaper headlines, and journalists often add idioms to the headline to make it figurative, expressive and dialogic. Unlike a phraseological unit that does not have complete information, a unit or a phraseological unit that expresses the topic of the article only with a supporting actant, such a title of journalistic material is not only evaluative, but also self-supporting in terms of information, often includes the mother. In this case, the title turns out to be evaluative information, its main semantic element (negative, positive) has a characteristic.

1. The subtitle, at some point, is loaded, ceases to carry the main semantic load and becomes level or, as a rule, becomes information in itself, which is a clarification and a potential reader. It is necessary to provide information. It helps to partially interpret the information material.

2. Title video without subtitles. In this case, the writer often does not use the title, because the environment of the phraseological unit plays the role of the title, and the actant accompanying it indicates the role of the same defining element as the superscript.

3. Newspapers: Ilin: "Lyon" will not go far with skill alone. You will not come far.

Why, who are you, what are you, with whom, with what. You can't achieve much, you can't achieve much. [Daily Mail 1986: 491].

This text contains only the title, no subtitle. A companion actant (on one skill) is included in the title, which means that such a title needs more information.

Cameron Diaz seriously offended the Peruvians. . "SUN" (25.06.2007)

NOT A JOKE. Very hard, deep, serious. [Observer 1986: 537].

The employee of the Ministry of Industry and Energy turned out to be dishonest

CLEAN BY HAND. Prone to theft, fraud; cheat, thief. [Independent 1986: 279].

Phraseologisms The accompanying actant with the following participle (compared to the adverbial word) offers greater opportunities for journalistic fantasy, because it, unlike the accompanying word, has freedom of semantic content, i.e. instead of the accompanying actant a semantic component defining the topic of the publication may appear, and at the same time the evaluation and expressiveness characteristic of phraseological rotation will be preserved.

In the dictionary entry of the phraseological dictionary, the accompanying actant is always indicated. It expands the headline's cognitive potential (its textual potential), and often such an evaluative and informative headline does not need a headline, as the accompanying actant guides the potential reader well in the publication material.

Conclusion . From the perspective of a functional approach, the headers can be displayed as follows:

- 1) the indicative-informational title provides the minimum level of information presentation and implies the direction of the reader to the material;
- 2) self-information provides the necessary level of presentation of information to a potential reader within the framework of concretization and partial interpretation of information material:
- 3) assessment-information, the main semantic element of which is assessment of fact (negative, positive).

The phraseological title turns out to be the most effective means of dialogizing speech due to the interaction of etymological and actual meanings, the ratio of the two language images of the world. It seems appropriate to include the term actant-, accompanist, which means words controlled by a phraseological unit and serving to realize its meaning. Realizing the corresponding syntactic valence of the phraseological unit, accompanying actants are widely used in newspaper headlines. There is a stable trend in the perception and use of a phraseological expression by the writer, and in many cases the phraseological unit is accepted as a linguistic unit and is repeated every time in its completed form. In a number of cases, the phraseological unit is enclosed in quotation marks, which indicates its formulaic nature, that is, the phraseology is taken as someone else's speech. In a sufficiently large sample size (which primarily refers to modified phraseological units), phraseology is used by the writer as a speech unit created according to a certain model each time.

The modified phraseological unit-heading is perceived by the writer as a language unit that is repeated every time in a ready form (as in a dictionary). A modified phraseological unit is used by the writer as a speech unit that is recreated each time according to a certain model.

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